

PHYSICAL VIOLENCE VICTIMIZATION AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS OF SOUTH MUMBAI

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Abstract

Transgender community face extreme exclusion in our society due to various misconceptions and reasons. The aim of the study was to explain attitudes of sample based on educational qualifications and the cisgender. Descriptive survey method was adopted to study the attitude of 540 respondents from various educational background. The t test results indicated that there is no significant difference between attitude of cisgender towards transgender. Further, ANOVA indicated that there is no significant difference in the attitude towards transgender based on educational qualification except between groups of respondents with SSC and others (below SSC). The results to a great extent indicates that education plays an important role in broadening horizons and accepting individuals as they are without any judgement. The present research was conducted to identify the physical violence victimization among college students in south Mumbai. The tool prepared by Goggins, (1998) was used for this study. The survey was conducted among 99 female students. The study revealed that the students with educational level from HSC, graduate and Postgraduate experience violence with an average frequency of "sometimes". The caretakers have been victimizing the students rather than the strangers and non-romantic acquaintances. The objective was to study the level of Physical Violence Experience among college students. The findings of the study revealed that the experience of victimization from a stranger is increasing from HSC to graduate and Graduate to Post graduate. Physical violence experiences have been reported by postgraduate students from authoritative persons and also from strangers. Respondents of this study have been victimized mainly by family members and authoritative figures rather than romantic, non-romantic and strangers.

Key Words: *Physical Violence Experience, South Mumbai, students, Educational Background*

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Introduction

Physical violence victimisation is considered as a long term effect on the mental well being of a person. Many researches were conducted on Physical victimisation of students by peers, siblings, family members. (Sullivan, 2006; Lento, 2006) Physical violence by a parental figure is usually termed as for disciplinary action. (Espelage, 2014) Baldry 2003 observed that children with violent parents are more involved in bullying and other type of physical violence. The parental corporal punishment is considered as one of the ways to disciplining children. Many researchers

reported that children experienced some sort of corporal punishment in their childhood may turn to abusers in adolescence. (Gershoff, 2002). The CP has harmful side effects reports by Straus in 2010.

Sibling violence is one of the more common forms of domestic violence. It is considered as the more controversial area of domestic violence. Graduate and post graduate education given emphasis to the development of sibling relationships. (Caffaro, 2013) Many researchers also reported Physical violence during socio-economic crisis. It is also reported that during the COVID 19 outbreak the physical violence by family members, caretakers are increased many fold (Polina, 2020)

Purpose of the Study

The researchers are working with an educational institution, wanted to know whether the students from metro city like South Mumbai had any experience of violence in their life. If so whether it is from strangers or some one who knows them well. Thus, the present paper is an attempt to highlight how students with varied academic level have been experiencing physical violence.

The researchers have attempted to find out physical violence victimization among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College.

Objectives of the Study

The following objective was formulated by researchers for the present study.

To study the level of Physical Violence Experience among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College.

Scope of the Study

The study mainly focuses on the Physical Violence Experience among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College. It includes only students of South Mumbai College. The study is restricted only to female students.

Delimitations of the Study

The study is restricted to students of South Mumbai College only. Only college students are included in the study. The study is limited to students of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College. The study does not include students from other professional or technical colleges.

Research Design

The method adopted for a study depends upon the nature and purpose of the study. The present research surveys the Physical Violence Experience among H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students of South Mumbai College. The sample consisted of only college students of South Mumbai. The sample consisted of 99 female college students. For the present study, the researchers have used the Descriptive method of the quantitative type. For the present study the researchers used the tool developed by Googins (1998). The tool helped to understand the physical violence experiences by respondents in five different areas.

Data Analysis

➤ The most common way of expressing aggression is in the form of spank, slap and pinch. The respondents were asked to give their frequency of experiencing such abuse in their life.

Table 1 Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of Physical Violence Experience in the form of spanked, slapped, pinched, hit, pushed, or grabbed, when the other person did NOT use a great deal of force

Education Background	H.S.C.			Graduates			Post-Graduates		
	Never	Some times	Very Frequently	Never	Some times	Very Frequently	Never	Some times	Very Frequently
1a	30.00	56.67	13.33	48.48	45.45	6.06	41.67	50.00	8.33
1b	53.33	26.67	20.00	48.48	42.42	9.09	58.33	25.00	16.67
1c	63.33	23.33	13.33	66.67	27.27	6.06	50.00	50.00	0.00
1d	63.33	23.33	13.33	75.76	21.21	3.03	66.67	33.33	0.00
1e	86.67	10.00	3.33	90.91	6.06	3.03	83.33	16.67	0.00
1f	70.00	20.00	10.00	72.73	24.24	3.03	41.67	41.67	16.67

Fig. 1 Showing Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of Physical Violence Experience in the form of spanked, slapped, pinched, hit, pushed, or grabbed, when the other person did NOT use a great deal of force

- Parent Figure (mother, step-father, grandparent who raised you, etc.)
- Other Family Members (brother, sister, cousin, etc.)
- Authority Figure (teacher, babysitter, coach, etc.)
- Non-romantic Acquaintance (friend, person at school, etc.)
- Romantic Acquaintance (dating partner, spouse, etc.)
- Stranger (person you've never met)

From table 1 and Figure 1, the physical violence experienced in the form of spank, slap, pinch

- 56% of HSC respondents reported they have been victimized from parental figure with the frequency "sometimes". The graduate students also almost the same around 45% experience violence from parental figures with frequency "sometimes".
- 42% reported other family members and 27% reported from authoritative around 20% from strangers and non romantic acquaintances with the average frequency of "sometimes".

- Post graduate students whose experience is little deviated from the two 50% respondents experience violence from parental figure as well as authoritative and 33% experience such violence from Non-romantic with frequency “Sometimes”. The experience of victimization from a stranger is increasing from HSC to graduate and Graduate to Post graduate. Physical violence experience have been reported by postgraduate students from authoritative person and also from stranger (16%) with” very frequently” frequency
- Many times it is observed that parents, teachers or relatives use some object to inflict violence. In the second section the respondents were asked to respond about their experiences.

Table 2 Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of Physical Violence Experience in the form of hit with an object (belt, switch, etc, but not a weapon such as a knife or gun) or had an object aggressively thrown at you

Education Background	H.S.C.			Graduates			Post-Graduates		
Physical Violence Experience	Never	Some times	Very Frequently	Never	Some times	Very Frequently	Never	Some times	Very Frequently
2a	66.67	30.00	3.33	72.73	24.24	3.03	91.67	8.33	0.00
2b	86.67	6.67	6.67	75.76	24.24	0.00	83.33	16.67	0.00
2c	86.67	13.33	0.00	90.91	6.06	3.03	75.00	25.00	0.00
2d	90.00	10.00	0.00	96.97	3.03	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
2e	96.67	3.33	0.00	96.97	0.00	3.03	91.67	8.33	0.00
2f	100.00	0.00	0.00	96.97	0.00	3.03	91.67	8.33	0.00

Fig. 2 Showing Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of Physical Violence Experience in the form of hit with an object (belt, switch, etc, but not a weapon such as a knife or gun) or had an object aggressively thrown at you

From table 2 & figure 2, the physical violence experience in the form of hit with an object,

- The research shows that mainly the people who are closely associated with the respondents, have been victimizing rather than a stranger or a romantic acquaintance.
- The physical violence experience (with frequency sometimes) of being hit with an object by a caretaker such as parents and grandparents shows a decline from HSC to PG (30%, 24%, 8%).

- Only 3% HSC and Graduate students reported frequency “very frequent” experience of hit with an object from parent figure 13%of HSC and 25% PG students reported that they have been experienced violence from authoritative figures too.
- Physical violence with an object with great force inflicts a traumatic experience .The respondents were asked to identify how frequently they are subjected to such trauma.

Table 3 Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of Physical Violence Experience in the form of shaken or hit with a great deal of force, kicked bitten, punched, shoved, pulled by the hair, choked, burned, or pinned down

Education Background	H.S.C.			Graduates			Post-Graduates		
	Never	Some times	Very Frequently	Never	Some times	Very Frequently	Never	Some times	Very Frequently
3a	76.67	16.67	6.67	90.91	9.09	0.00	91.67	8.33	0.00
3b	83.33	13.33	3.33	84.85	15.15	0.00	75.00	25.00	0.00
3c	86.67	6.67	6.67	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
3d	90.00	6.67	3.33	100.00	0.00	0.00	83.33	16.67	0.00
3e	96.67	3.33	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	91.67	8.33	0.00
3f	96.67	0.00	3.33	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00

Fig. 3 Showing Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of Physical Violence Experience in the form of shaken or hit with a great deal of force, kicked bitten, punched, shoved, pulled by the hair, choked, burned, or pinned down

From table 3 and fig 3 , the physical violence experience in the form of shaken or hit with a great deal of force, kicked, bitten, punched, shoved, pulled by the hair, choked, burned, or pinned down is a punishable offence.

- We can observe from the data 13 to 15% HSC and Graduate students have been reported that they are the victims of such violence from parental figures and other family members.

- The post graduate students are sometimes victims of such violence from relatives (25%) and non romantic acquaintances (16%).
- 8% of PG students report experiencing such violence from parents and romantic acquaintances too.
- Threatening is another way of violence. In this section the respondents were asked to identify how frequently they were threatened

Table 4 Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of Physical Violence Experience in the form of threatened (but the person did NOT follow through) with physical aggression or an object (not involving a weapon)

Education Background	H.S.C.			Graduates			Post-Graduates		
	Never	Some times	Very Frequently	Never	Some times	Very Frequently	Never	Some times	Very Frequently
4a	83.33	13.33	3.33	87.88	9.09	3.03	50.00	50.00	0.00
4b	90.00	10.00	0.00	90.91	9.09	0.00	66.67	33.33	0.00
4c	86.67	13.33	0.00	96.97	3.03	0.00	75.00	25.00	0.00
4d	93.33	3.33	3.33	93.94	6.06	0.00	83.33	16.67	0.00
4e	93.33	6.67	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	91.67	8.33	0.00
4f	96.67	0.00	3.33	96.97	3.03	0.00	91.67	8.33	0.00

Fig. 4 Showing Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of Physical Violence Experience in the form of threatened (but the person did NOT follow through) with physical aggression or an object (not involving a weapon)

From the table 4 & figure 4, research shows that

- The threats from parents, relatives and teachers are experienced by HSC, graduates and Postgraduates. But Post graduate students reported they have experienced such violence from Parent figure (50%) with frequency

“Sometimes”, relatives (33%) and from authoritative figure (25%). But this experience by HSC and Graduates is below 15%.

- In the 5th question which is related to violence in the form of threat associated with an object. The respondents were asked about how frequently they experience such violence.

Table 5 Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of Physical Violence Experience in the form of threatened with a weapon (knife, gun, etc.) or had a weapon used

Education Background	H.S.C.			Graduates			Post-Graduates		
	Never	Some times	Very Frequently	Never	Some times	Very Frequently	Never	Some times	Very Frequently
5a	96.67	0.00	3.33	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
5b	93.33	3.33	3.33	96.97	3.03	0.00	91.67	8.33	0.00
5c	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
5d	96.67	3.33	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
5e	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
5f	96.67	3.33	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00

Fig. 5 Showing Percentage of H.S.C., Graduates & Post Graduate students level of Physical Violence Experience in the form of threatened with a weapon (knife, gun, etc.) or had a weapon used

From table 5 and Fig 5, Experience of PV (Physical Violence) such as threatening along showing with a weapon, shows that very few participants have such an experience,

- 8% PG Students and 3% graduates and HSC students have been victimized.

- Also 3% of HSC students reported the violence at the frequency of “Very frequently”

Table 6 OVERALL Percentage of level of Physical Violence Experience

Physical Violence Experience			1	2	3	4	5
a	Parent Figure (mother, step-father, grandparent who raised you, etc.)	N	40	78	87	73	99
		S	51	20	11	25	0
		VF	9	2	2	2	1
b	Other Family Member (brother, sister, cousin, etc.)	N	54	82	81	82	94
		S	31	16	18	18	5
		VF	15	2	1	0	1
c	Authority Figure (teacher, babysitter, coach, etc.)	N	60	84	96	86	100
		S	34	15	2	14	0
		VF	6	1	2	0	0
d	Nonromantic Acquaintance (friend, person at school, etc.)	N	69	96	91	90	99
		S	26	4	8	9	1
		VF	5	0	1	1	0
e	Romantic Acquaintance (dating partner, spouse, etc.)	N	87	95	96	95	100
		S	11			5	0
		VF	2	1	0	0	0
f	Stranger (person you've never met)	N	97	96	99	95	99
		S	3	3	0	4	1
		VF	0	1	1	1	0

Fig. 6 Showing Percentage of level of Physical Violence Experience

From the table 6 & fig 6 it is evident that respondents of this study have been victimized mainly by family members and authoritative figures rather than romantic, non romantic and strangers.

Major findings

1. The students with all the levels of education have reported physical violence experiences.
2. The students at all levels victimised more from parental, relative and authoritative figure than stranger and romantic Acquaintance
3. Extreme levels of Physical violence using an object with force is also been reported by all the levels.

Recommendations:

There should be stringent punishment in the law against the prefectures of physical violence

The teachers and parents should be oriented towards the ill effects of physical violence and its impact on the well-being of students.

Conclusion:

From the findings it may be concluded that H.S.C. & Graduates students and between Graduates & Post Graduates students have been reported physical violence experience. The students at all levels victimised more from parental, relative and authoritative figures than stranger and romantic Acquaintance. Extreme levels of Physical violence using an object with force have also been reported by students of all the levels.

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